

QUALITY ASSURANCE INDICES AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SOCIAL STUDIES CURRICULUM IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM NORTHEAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study aims to determine how quality assurance indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population of this study consists of all the 288 teachers (192 Social Studies teachers and 96 Heads of Department of Humanities) drawn from the 96 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. The sample size comprises 167 teachers (111 Social Studies teachers and 56 heads of humanities) obtained through Taro Yamane formula. Simple random sampling technique was used for this study. A researcher-developed questionnaire tagged “Quality Assurance Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum Questionnaire” (QAISSCQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts in the Department of Social Studies and Citizenship Education, University of Uyo. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability method and .86 reliability index was obtained. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used in answering the research questions as well as testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that teacher quality, teaching facility, and time allocation indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. Based on this, it was recommended, among others, that Government through State Secondary Education Board should ensure that the right calibers of teachers are recruited and deployed to public secondary schools for effective implementation of social studies curriculum.

Keywords: Quality Assurance Indices, Teacher Quality, Teaching Facility, Time Allocation, Implementation, Social Studies Curriculum.

Introduction

A significant aspect of the Nigerian National Policy on Education is the demarcation of the Junior Secondary School (JSS) curriculum into both academic and pre-vocational electives. The Academic (core) subjects include English, Mathematics, Nigerian Languages, Science, Social Studies, Music, Arts, Practical Agriculture, Religious and Moral Instructions, Physical Education and two Pre-vocational subjects (Federal Republic of Nigeria [FRN], 2013). Social studies is one of the core compulsory subjects taught at the JSS level (Upper Basic Education category). Social studies is needed in laying a solid foundation for the teaching of subjects like economics, geography and history at the Senior Secondary School (SSS) level and courses such as anthropology, philosophy, political science, psychology and sociology at tertiary institutions.

Social studies denotes integrated and unified subject that attempts to examine and improve upon the political, socio-cultural, religious and economic life of the people. The acceptance and introduction of social studies as a curriculum subject in the Nigerian education sector was pertinent because of the enormity of the socio-political problems which almost led to the disintegration of the country. Ikwumelu *et al.* (2015) agreed that Nigeria, being a pluralistic society was faced with the challenge of conflicting values. In view of this, social studies as a subject full of values and virtues instructions is saddled with the task of sustaining peaceful coexistence of the Nigerian people. Social studies curriculum provides a vital forum for developing the thinking skills, values and attitudes that make the 'good citizen' and equip people for coping with change. As a product of social studies education, a good citizen should possess good orientation and positive attitude toward other people's culture and religious beliefs. Despite the relevance of social studies and its teaching for over some years now, it has been realized that Nigerian children and youth are still involved in socio-political, cultural and religious crises in the country. As a matter of fact, the levels of crime and crises in the Nigerian society do not show that majority of these citizens have been exposed to a core subject like social studies which has the focus of producing a good citizen.

Social studies curriculum is a well-designed programme with provision for adequate contents, performance objectives and recommended instructional strategies. It suggests activities for teachers and learners and recommends appropriate instructional materials to exert influence and brings positive change in the learners. It also contains evaluation guide to assess learner's level of achievement at every stage of the teaching and learning process in social studies class. But it is not certain whether stakeholders are faithfully committed to the implementation of its

curriculum. Social studies curriculum is designed and developed to be implemented for the benefit of the society for which it was developed. The value and beauty of social studies curriculum is appreciated when it is being implemented.

Implementation is the process of carrying out a programme according to the prescribed rules. According to Obadiora (2019), implementing social studies curriculum entails the process of executing the design as described and prescribed by the curriculum toward the attainment of a particular objective. Obviously, the implementation must follow rules presented in the document, the way it was intended to be implemented by the developers. This is what National Centre on Early Childhood Development, Teaching and Learning (NCECDTL) (2011) regard as implementation fidelity. According to NCECDTL, assessors of curriculum implementation should be concerned about the quality assurance indices such as whether qualified staff was used, whether staff focused on the specific goals identified in the lesson plans, whether staff used the recommended teaching strategies, or whether staff used recommended and appropriate instructional materials.

The concern for quality in the education service delivery necessitated the adoption of quality assurance in education as an emerging policy strategy in contemporary world which emanated from the world conference on Education for All initiated by UNESCO (Nwite and Nkiru, 2017). Representatives of the international community agreed that all countries should pay greater attention towards improving all secondary education aspects of education (quality) and ensure excellence at all levels (Nwite and Nkiru, 2017). Quality is something good, ideal or high standard. Quality education provided by trained and supported teachers are said to be the right of every citizen and not the privilege of the few. Any statement about quality implies a certain relative measure against a common standard. In education, quality emphasizes teachers' competence, creativity, commitment, and how educational administrators organize school activities in order to realize the full potentials of all personnel in educational institutions (Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo, 2018). It is the appropriateness and relevance of resources available for the achievement of educational goals and priorities, hence, quality in education whether primary, secondary or tertiary institutions requires adequate input and outputs.

Quality assurance in education is the efficient management, monitoring, evaluation and reviews of the resource inputs and transformation (teaching and learning) to produce a quality output (students) that meets set standards and expectations of the society (Ayeni and Afolabi, 2012). This has been an issue of great concern among

education stakeholders in the country as to what could mar the desire result of the school system in several States of Nigeria. According to Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo (2018), most parents in Akwa Ibom State and specifically, Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District are of the view that private schools are better managed with a relatively higher standard of education, well behaved students with less disciplinary problems, better facilities, better performance in examinations, and higher quality output. The authors revealed that the quality of public secondary schools has come under severe criticism from stakeholders in the last few years, and it has become imperative for the deployment of some mechanisms to control and improve the educational quality. Certainly, this could be the cause of consistent poor academic achievement in social studies, high rate of examination malpractice and high drop-out rate, among others, in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. The performance of students in this subject at the JSS level could therefore influence their choice of career if still remain unabated. It is against this background that this study sought to determine the quality assurance indices and implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary school in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Teacher's Quality and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum

The qualitatively trained social studies teacher is an asset and strategic figure in the effective implementation of social studies curriculum at the upper basic level in Nigeria. Experts opinions tend to suggests that there are many non-professionally trained social studies teachers teaching social studies at the upper basic education level (Okam, 2012; Mezieobi, 2013; Akinola, 2014 and Ikem, 2014). This issue revealed that social studies is not effectively implemented to achieve its transformative objectives of producing functional citizens into values, skills, attitudes and cognition for realizing integrated, collaborative and inter dependent national development. Mezieobi *et al.* (2012) noted that the effective implementation of social studies curriculum in schools is inextricably dependent on quality of social studies teachers who are adequately informed about what to teach, attitudes, values and skills expected to be injected in the learners for the realization of functional educational goals. Obadiora (2019) also noted that effective implementation of social studies curriculum is synonymous with teaching (teachers) effectiveness.

In addition, it can be seen as a manifestation of knowledge of content, skills in lesson presentation, creating desirable atmosphere for learning and also as a kind of classroom transactions that occur between teachers and students resulting in increase in students' knowledge. It is the achievement of all or most of the learning objectives and reduction of differences in cognitive levels among the students. Social studies teachers' classroom instructional effectiveness is instrumental to the effective

implementation of the social studies curriculum in schools (Mezieobi *et al.*, 2012)). According to Federal Republic of Nigeria [FRG] (2013), the quality of effective teaching is dependent on the capability of trained social studies teachers and ability to simulate learning to an appreciable extent. Akeke and Aluko (2017) asserted that the method adopted by social studies teachers is a strong factor that can affect learners' level of achievement. These days, many people can be teachers, but the question is, how many people are qualified?

Social studies teachers are the crux of subjects' implementation and without them teaching effectively, the subjects may not attain its objectives. Obadiora (2019) opined that teachers are expected to adopt various instructional approaches, illustrations and explanations, such that the learner is maximally involved in the teaching/learning environment. Effective teachers presuppose effective learning by students. Teaching effectiveness can be seen as a teacher's ability to be intellectually challenging, motivating students, setting high standards, approachable, presenting materials well, making social studies and class interesting, encouraging self-initiated learning and having good elocutionary skills that triggers learning and produce useful outcome (Akeke and Aluko, 2017)

Teaching Facilities Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum

Teaching facilities are everything used directly or indirectly for the purpose of teaching and learning. It can also be explained as the entire school plant such as classrooms, staff rooms, laboratories, workshops, libraries, consumables, audiovisual aids, water, electricity, tables, stationeries, and playgrounds (Inyang-Abia, 2016). The teacher's ingenuity in improving, adopting and maximizing the utilization of the scarce and often insufficient teaching facilities can have a tremendous impact on the successful teaching and learning of social studies (Alimi, 2014). Teaching facilities are vehicles that carry messages from the transmitter (teacher) to the receiver (students). The use of a teaching facility as a tool in the application of the entire curriculum content cannot be overlooked, thus making knowledge feasible. With the help of these facilities, policies can be transmitted into facts. Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo (2018) enumerated the educational values of teaching facilities to include the following: i. Provision of direct or firsthand experience on the realities of the social and physical school environment. ii. Promotion of meaningful communication for effective teaching and learning. iii. Ensuring better communication and retention of information thus, making teaching, learning and recall more permanent. iv. Stimulation and motivation of teachers and pupils towards feasible teaching and learning. v. Arousal of teachers' and learners' interest in all areas of teaching and learning. vi. Encourage teachers and pupils' active participation,

especially subsequent teaching and learning permit manipulation of materials used.
vii. Provision of a common experience upon which other learning can be based.

Teaching facilities are provided by the schools for the purpose of enhancing teaching and learning. It includes the classrooms, laboratories, laboratory equipment, school furniture, chalkboard, tools and machine, audio and audiovisual aids, etc. The importance of teaching facilities cannot be over-emphasized as they help to promote teaching and learning in the school system. Commenting on the importance of teaching facilities in schools, Ogbonna and Nnana (2013) maintained that learning takes place better and faster in school environments with high level of buildings, accommodation, furniture, and equipment than an environment where these items are lacking. Teachers too, cannot teach effectively without adequate teaching facilities. School location and teaching facilities play a vital role in determining the academic achievement of students in social Studies. Indeed, the quality of student academic achievement is a function of various interventions

Time Allocation Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum

Time is an immaterial resource, inelastic, scarce and erodes fast and once spent, cannot be won back, stored or recalled for use. Kalu (2012) supported that time is an essential resource, irrecoverable, limited and dynamic. Irrecoverable because every minute spent is gone forever, limited because only 24hours exist in a day and dynamic because it is never static. Adejo (2012) stated that managing time appropriately leads to achieving results easily with limited resources. Consequently, any productive system, whatever its structure, human or technology requires efficient and effective time allocation procedure.

Time allocation is probably not as easy as what it is imagined and expected to be. According to Kayode and Ayodele (2015), time allocation is the organization of tasks or events by first estimating how much time a task will take to be completed, when it must be completed, and then adjusting events that would interfere with its completion in the appropriate amount of time. Khan and Farooqi (2016) asserted that time allocation involves identifying tasks to be performed, planning and scheduling of organizational activities, prioritizing such activities, allocating time to the tasks according to degree of importance in enhancing productivity, minimizing interruptions and frivolities. Kayode and Ayodele (2015) asserted that the types of behaviour that differentiate people who do things on time, stick to deadline and spend little time on activities from those who are often late, pass deadline, spend much time on their activities and waste time on unimportant matters are critical when referring to allotted time.

Maduagwu (2011) asserted that if the principal is to facilitate teaching and learning, how one schedules the various tasks and allocates commensurate amount of time to the various tasks, determines to a large extent the productivity level of the teacher. Principals spend a lot of time each day planning, organizing, controlling, holding meetings and communicating. Kayode and Ayodele (2015) highlighted the following as some of the importance of time allotted which contributes to the success of teacher, reduces misunderstanding and confusion about the essential duties; creates time and opportunity for carrying out the essential duties; reduces conflicts in schedules, activities and interpersonal relations; facilitates delegation of duties to teachers; increases the productivity of teachers; makes easy for teacher to meet deadlines. Ugwulashi (2011) maintained that there are scheduled times for every activity; principals budget and legitimate the time to accomplish set goals as well as compare the total estimated time for expected maturity task to enable teachers focus. This is in consonance with Maduagwu (2011) who noted that every activity of teacher in the implementation of social studies curriculum is allocated some frames of time within which the activities are to be accomplished in schools.

Statement of the Problem

A major problem that constantly attracts public concern about secondary education is its seeming inability to achieve its basic goals of producing quality school leavers with the capacity to contribute to national development. More worrisome is the fact that most school leavers completed this level of education without acquiring basic functional literacy skills, arithmetic and effective communication that enhance functionality and progress in higher education; thus, becoming liabilities and posing threats to their immediate environment. This has resulted in hooliganism, gangsterism, kidnapping and all forms of social malaise as a result of frustration and idleness. Of course, the issue could be accredited to lack of or poor quality assurance indices that ensure effective teaching and learning for the inculcation of the right type of knowledge, skills, value, and attitudes or attainment of the goals of secondary education. This may be ameliorated if quality assurance indices such as qualified teachers, teaching facilities, and time allocation are prioritized.

Educators and researchers have expressed serious concern over the state of teaching and learning of some subjects in schools all over the country. Social studies is not left out as it is often taught by unqualified teachers, with poor teaching facilities, inadequate time allocation, among others. Again, observation by the researcher shows that there are flaws in the implementation of social studies curriculum in Nigerian public secondary schools, especially those in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. As a result, the aims of secondary school seem difficult to attain. It

is on this note that this study seeks to determine the quality assurance indices and implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine how quality assurance indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. Teacher's quality indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.
2. Teaching facility indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.
3. Time allocation indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How do teachers' quality indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District?
2. How do teaching facility indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District?
3. How do time allocation indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** Teachers' quality indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.
- H₀₂:** Teaching facility indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.
- H₀₃:** Time allocation indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. According to Udoh and Joseph (2005), descriptive survey design is a technique for obtaining data from people through the use of questionnaire. Therefore, this design is considered suitable since information on quality assurance indices were sought from social studies teachers in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District using questionnaire. The population of this study consisted of all the 288 teachers (192 Social Studies teachers and 96 heads of department of humanities) drawn from the 96 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District (Statistic Unit, State Secondary Education Board, Headquarters, Uyo, 2022). Using a simple random sampling technique, a sample size of 167 teachers (58 % of population) was obtained through Taro Yamane formula.

The researcher developed questionnaire captioned “Quality Assurance Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum Questionnaire” (QAISSCQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was designed according to the independent and dependent variables in the study. It was divided into two parts (A and B). Part 'A' contained the personal data of the respondents. Part 'B' contained the statements on the variables grouped into clusters (A, B and C), namely teachers' quality, teaching facilities, and time allocation indices. The 4-points response options were used: Strongly Agree - (SA) - 4 points, Agree - (A) - 3 points, Disagree - (D) - 2 points and Strongly Disagree - (SD) - 1 point. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts in the Department of Social Studies and Citizenship Education, University of Uyo.

The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability method and a reliability index of 0.86 was obtained which showed that the instrument was reliable for the study. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used in answering the research questions as well as testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The R value and the associated nature of predictions as suggested by Joshua (2005) were adopted as guidelines for interpreting and taking decisions with regards to research questions as follows: +1.00 - Perfect prediction, +0.50 to 0.99 - High (strong) prediction, and +0.01 to 0.49 - Low (weak) prediction. In testing the null hypotheses, the p-value was compared with .05 level of significance. When ($p \leq .05$) less than or equal to .05, the null hypotheses (H_0) was rejected. On the other hand, when the p-value greater than ($p > .05$) the .05, the null hypotheses was retained.

Results

Research question 1

How do teachers' quality indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District?

Table 1: Regression Analysis showing how Teachers' Quality Indices predict Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District n = 167

Mode	R	R - Squar	Adjusted R-Square	Std Error of the estimate	Decisio
1	0.890	0.793	0.79	2.80024	High prediction

Table 1 with R value of 0.890 indicates that teachers' quality indices prediction on implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District is high. Additionally, the positive value of the adjusted R square indicates positive prediction. The R square of 0.793 implies that teachers' quality indices account for 79.3% prediction on implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Research Question 2

How does teaching facility indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District?

Table 2: Regression Analysis showing how Teaching Facility Indices predict Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial Districtn = 167

Mode	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std Error of the estimate	Decision
1	0.808	0.653	0.652	1.03254	High prediction

Table 2 with R value of 0.808 indicates that teaching facility indices prediction on implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District is high. Additionally, the positive value of the adjusted R square indicates positive prediction. The R square of 0.653 implies that teaching facility indices account for 65.3% prediction on implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Research question 3

How do time allocation indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District?

Table 3: Regression Analysis showing how Time Allocation Indices predict Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District n = 167

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted	R-Square	Std Error of the estimate	Decision
1	0.857	0.735	0.734	0.889	4.2	High prediction

Table 3 with R value of 0.857 shows that time allocation indices prediction on implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District is high. Additionally, the positive value of the adjusted R square indicates positive prediction. The R square of 0.735 implies that time allocation indices account for 73.5% prediction on implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Null Hypothesis 1

Teachers' quality indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

Table 4: Regression Analysis on Teacher Quality Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District n = 167

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	p-value	Decision
1 Regression	1249.205	1	1249.205	.000	Reject H ₀
Residual	326.600	165	.640		
Total	1575.805	166			

Table 4 reveals that the p-value of .000 is less than .05 level of significance. The prediction is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that teacher quality indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District is rejected. This shows that teacher quality indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Null Hypothesis 2

Teaching facility indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Table 5: Regression Analysis on Teaching Facility Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District n = 167

M o d e l	Sum of Squares	d	f	Mean Square	p - value	Decision
1 Regression	1 0 2 4 . 0 1 3	1		1 0 2 4 . 0 1 3	. 0 0 0	
Residual	5 5 1 . 7 9 2	1 6 5	1	. 0 6 6		Reject H ₀
T o t a l	1 5 7 5 . 8 0 5	1 6 6				

Table 5 reveals that the p-value of .000 is less than .05 level of significance. The prediction is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that teaching facility indices does not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District is rejected. This implies that teaching facility indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Null Hypothesis 3

Time allocation indices **do** not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Table 6: Regression Analysis on Time Allocation Indices and Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District n = 167

M o d e l	Sum of Squares	d	f	Mean Square	p - value	Decision
1 Regression	1 1 1 6 . 5 2 0	1		1 1 1 6 . 5 2 0	. 0 0 4	
Residual	4 0 3 . 4 4 7	1 6 5		. 7 9 1		Reject H ₀
T o t a l	1 5 1 9 . 9 6 7	1 6 6				

Table 6 reveals that the p-value of .004 is less than .05 level of significance. The prediction is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that time allocation indices do not significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District is rejected. This implies that time allocation indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

The finding on research question 1 and null hypothesis 1 revealed that teacher quality indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public

secondary schools in the target area. This finding is in congruence with the findings of Meziobi et al. (2012) who maintained that effective implementation of social studies curriculum in schools is inextricably dependent on quality of social studies teachers who are adequately informed about what to teach, attitudes, values and skills expected to be injected in the learners for the realization of functional educational goals.

The finding on research question 2 and null hypothesis 2 revealed that teaching facilities indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. This finding is supported by the findings of Ogbonna and Nnana (2013) who asserted that learning takes place better and faster in school environments with high level of buildings, accommodation, furniture, and equipment than an environment where these items are lacking. Teachers too, cannot teach effectively without adequate teaching facilities.

The finding on research question 3 and null hypothesis 3 revealed that time allocation indices significantly predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. This finding is in congruence with the findings of Kayode and Ayodele (2015) who maintained that time allocation is the organization of tasks or events by first estimating how much time a task will take to be completed, when it must be completed, and then adjusting events that would interfere with its completion in the appropriate amount of time.

Conclusion

This study was able to make various observations about the prediction between the quality assurance indices and implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. It is quite obvious that teacher quality, teaching facilities, and time allocation indices predict implementation of social studies curriculum in public secondary schools which would eventually result in promoting the students' academic achievement in social studies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government through State Secondary Education Board should ensure that the right calibers of teachers are recruited and deployed to public secondary schools for effective implementation of social studies curriculum.
2. Government through State Secondary Education Board should also ensure that there is provision as well as availability of adequate teaching facilities in public

- secondary schools for effective implementation of social studies curriculum.
3. The school principals, heads of the humanities units, and social studies teachers should work cooperatively to ensure that adequate time is fairly allotted for the effective teaching of social studies in the school devoid of bias and prioritization of some school subjects.

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